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DEVELOPMENT OF UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ASSAY METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF IVABRADINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND FORMULATED MICROSPHERE DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Ivabradine is a heart rate lowering agent and controls the spontaneous diastolic depolarization in the sinus node to regulates heart rate. It is soluble in water, hydrochloric acid and in methanol. A simple, sensitive, precise and highly accurate UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for determination of Ivabradine HCL in formulated microsphere dosage form. Ivabradine HCl exhibited λ max at 286 nm in water, 0.1 N HCL solution and obeyed linearity in the concentration range of 20-100 mcg with Coefficient of determination value (R^2) of 0.9960. The slope, intercept, correlation coefficient, detection and quantitation limits were also calculated and found within statistical perimeter. Result of percentage recovery shows the method was not influenced by the presence of impurities or excipients. The method was validated by determining its sensitivity, accuracy and precision which proves suitability of the developed method for the routine estimation of Ivabradine in microsphere dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION

Ivabradine is 3-[3-[[[(7S)-3,4-dimethoxy-7-bicyclo[4.2.0]octa-1,3,5-trienyl]methyl-methylamino]propyl]-7,8-dimethoxy-2,5-dihydro-1H-3-benzazepin-4-one;hydrochloride. which is a pure heart rate lowering agent, acting by selective and specific inhibition of the cardiac pacemaker I_f current that controls the spontaneous diastolic depolarization in the sinus node and regulates heart rate. The main pharmacodynamic property of Ivabradine in humans is a specific dose dependent reduction in heart rate. Analysis of heart rate reduction with doses up to 20 mg twice daily indicates a trend towards a plateau effect which is consistent with a reduced risk of severe bradycardia below 40 bpm^[1].

Ivabradine HCL is rapidly and almost completely absorbed after oral administration with a peak plasma level reached in about 1 hour under fasting condition. The absolute bioavailability is around 40%, due to first-pass effect in the gut and liver. Food delayed absorption by approximately 1 hour, and increased plasma exposure by 20 to 30 %.^[1,2]. Ivabradine does not have a pharmacopoeia monograph. As a consequence, the reference method for ivabradine determination is not universally accepted. Ivabradine frequently appears in the scientific writing, but a monograph describing the method of its determination is still not sufficient. Though a stability indicating HPLC Method has been reported, it has its own limitation.

The aim and objective of this study is to develop a easy, precise and, rapid Ultraviolet Spectroscopic method for estimation of ivabradine hydrochloride in microsphere formulations as per ICH guidelines which is easily adaptable as a routine in quality testing laboratories in industry and academic institutes.

Properties of Ivabradine HCl:

Chemical formula^[3,4]: C₂₇H₃₇ClN₂O₅

Average Molar mass: 505.052 g/mol.

Fig. 01 Structure of Ivabradine HCL.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Ivabradine HCL is provided as gift sample by Biocon Limited , Pashamylaram, Andhrapradesh, India. All the chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade (AR) procured from Merck. All absorbance measurements were done with Shimadzu 1601 double beam UV-Spectrophotometer (Japan) with 10mm matched quartz cell and Borosil glass wares were used for the study. All weighing were done on single pan balance Dhona 200 D.

Method

Preparation of Stock Solutions

Accurately weighed 100 mg of Ivabradine was dissolved in 0.1N HCl in a 100ml volumetric flask to prepare stock solution.

Preparation of Working Standard Solutions

A set of standard dilutions of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100µg/ml of drug were prepared by transferring aliquots of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1 ml stock solution (100µg/ml) in 10ml volumetric flask and volume make up to the mark with medium.

Selection of wavelength

Working standard solution having concentration 20 µg/ml was scanned using spectrophotometer within UV range i.e 200–400 nm against water as blank^[4,5]. Wavelength 286 nm was selected for estimations from the UV spectrum obtained as below figure 02. The optical density values of above solutions were measured using 1cm cells at 286 nm using 0.1 N hydrochloric acid as a blank and recorded in the table 01 with statistical data in table 02. The concentration versus absorbance values are plotted and given in figure 03.

Fig. 02 Spectrum of Ivabradine HCL.

Beers law study:

Absorbance of each working solution was measured at the selected wavelength 286 nm. Calibration curve was constructed by taking absorbance on Y axis and concentration on X axis as shown below in figure 3.

Table 01 Observation table of beers law study.

Sr. No.	Concentration of Ivabradine $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance at 286 nm
1.	0	0
2.	20	0.282 \pm 0.002
3.	40	0.539 \pm 0.0014
4.	60	0.773 \pm 0.0015
5.	80	1.037 \pm 0.013
6.	100	1.393 \pm 0.002

n = 3, all values \pm standard deviation.

Fig. 03 Calibration curve of Ivabradine HCL.

Table 02 Calibration Curve Data and Regression Values of Ivabradine HCL in 0.1 N HCL.

Absorption maxima	286 nm
Best Fit Values	
Slope	0.0137 ± 0.0004271
Y Intercept	- 0.0035 ± 0.02586
1/Slope	72.99
95% Confidence Interval	
Y-intercept	-0.0435 to 0.03655
Goodness of Fit	
R square	0.998
P Value	< 0.0001
Equation	Y = 0.0137x - 0.0035

Formula:

Concentration of test solutions were calculated by using slope and intercept equation obtained from the calibration curve of Ivabradine HCL.

Slope and intercept equation: $y = m x + c$

Where, y is y axis value i.e. Absorbance
x is x axis value i.e. Concentration

Assay:

Formulated Microspheres of Ivabradine HCL were triturated in mortal & pestal to obtained drug powder equivalent to 5 mg of Ivabradine, transferred to 10 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in 0.1 N HCL. Solution was sonicated for 15 min and filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41 and it was further diluted to get the requisite concentration. The absorbance of the prepared sample solution was measured against 0.1 N HCL as a blank at 286 nm.

Table 03 Observation Table of Assay.

Claim of IVB in Microsphere Formulation (mg)	Drug found (mg/tablet)	% Purity
05 mg	5.02 mg	100.4
05 mg	4.92 mg	98.4
05 mg	4.98 mg	99.6
	Mean	99.46667
Statistical values for n=3	SD	1.006645
	%RSD	1.012042

Recovery Studies

Recovery studies were carried out by standard addition method at three different levels 80%, 100% and 120%. The % recovery of Ivabradine in the sample mixture was determined. The results of analysis and recovery studies obtained by proposed method were validated by statistical evaluation and are recorded in Table 04.

Table 04 Observation Table of Recovery Studies.

Level of Recovery	Amount of Pure drug added (mg)	% Recovery
80%	4	99.42
100%	5	99.66
120%	6	99.80
	Mean	99.62
Mean % Recovery	SD	0.192
	% RSD	0.1927

SD is a standard deviation, CV is coefficient of variation, SE is standard error

Validation:**Precision:**

The precision of the proposed method was ascertained by actual determination of three replicates of fixed concentration of the drug within the Beer's range and finding out the absorbance by the proposed method. From these absorbance mean, Standard deviation and % RSD were calculated.

Table 05 Observation Table of Precision.

Claim of IVB in Microsphere Formulation (mg)	Drug found (mg)	% Purity
05	5.05 mg	101
05	5.04 mg	100.8
05	4.97 mg	99.4
	Mean	100.4
Statistical values for n=3	SD	0.87178
	%RSD	0.868307

Linearity and Range study

Accurately weighed quantity of drug sample was diluted to obtain concentration in the range of 80-120 % of test concentration. Absorbance of each solution was recorded at 286 nm. It is found that sample obeys linearity over 80 -120 % of test concentration. Least square regression analysis was performed on the obtained data. Linearity study data and linearity graph are shown in table 06 and figure 04 respectively.

Table 06 Observation table of Linearity and Range Study.

Sr. No.	Wt. of sample in mg	%Label claim	Absorbance at 286 nm
1.	04	80	0.529
2.	4.5	90	0.603
3.	05	100	0.673
4.	5.5	110	0.735
5.	06	120	0.801

Fig. 04 Linearity and range curve of Ivabradine HCL.

Accuracy

To ascertain the accuracy of the proposed methods, recovery studies were carried out by the standard addition method at three different levels (80%, 100 % & 120 %) of the bulk sample of Ivabradine HCl to the previously analyzed solution of mixture of Ivabradine and excipient. The percentage recovery was found to be in the range of (98.00 % - 102 %) as shown in table.

Sensitivity

Sensitivity of the proposed method was determined in terms of limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ were calculated using formulae

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{s}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{s}$$

where 'σ' is the standard deviation (n=5) taken as a measure of noise, and 's' is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

Table 07 Observation table of Sensitivity Study.

Standard deviation n=5	Slope	LOD	LOQ
0.00052	0.01351	0.134899	0.408785

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A simple and appreciable UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for estimation of Ivabradine in bulk and Microsphere formulation. Working solution of drug in 0.1 N HCl was scanned between 200 to 400 nm in UV Spectrophotometer and 286 nm was selected as wavelength of maximum absorbance. Beer's law was obeyed by drug in the concentration range of 20-100 µg/ml. Correlation coefficient, slope, intercept and Standard Deviation were calculated and are summarized in table no 2. Results of the recovery study were validated on the basis of accuracy, linearity, range, LOD and LOQ. Developed method found fast, economical, selective and sensitive for the estimation of Ivabradine from bulk and microsphere formulation.

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Conflict of Interest Statement:

The authors affirm that no conflict of interest exists among them.

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